

Aligning rTWT with 802.1Qbv: a Network Calculus Approach

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ABSTRACT

Industry 4.0 applications impose the challenging demand of delivering packets with bounded latencies via a wireless network. This is further complicated if the network is not dedicated to the time critical application. In this paper we use network calculus analysis to derive closed form expressions of latency bounds for time critical traffic when 802.11 Target Wake Time (TWT) and 802.1Qbv work together in a shared 802.11 network.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Networks** → **Network performance analysis**; *Network performance modeling*.

KEYWORDS

Network Calculus, Scheduling, 802.11Qbv, restricted Target Wake Time (rTWT)

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1 INTRODUCTION

Unscheduled channel access in 802.11 networks negatively impacts their reliability particularly in dense deployments. This is a particularly challenging phenomenon given the imminent use of wireless networks for industry 4.0 applications [5]. TWT reduces contention by allowing the AP to instruct Station (STA)s to turn their transceivers on or off at agreed intervals. The discipline thus transforms a dense deployment to one with a manageable number of STAs during a TWT session therefore reducing contention and improving the radio channel access delay. Moreover, 802.11be will extend it to restricted Target Wake Time (rTWT) to completely eliminate contention¹. This method has been proposed as a scheduling mechanism in [1] that achieves improvement in overall network throughput but does not consider the priority of packets. This approach is therefore inadequate for Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) flows requiring bounded latency. We propose an enhancement, incorporating TSN, by aligning channel access via rTWT with 802.1Qbv scheduling. The authors of [3] provide a proof

¹In 802.11ax contention can be ameliorated with techniques such as trigger-based Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA).

Figure 1: An STA (middle) with two 802.1Qbv queues of high q and low priority q' . The opening times of 802.1Qbv gates are aligned with the rTWT sessions (bottom). The STA has a single RU in the MU Tx scheduled within each TWT session. On top, the resulting network calculus service curves $\beta_{q'}^*, \beta_{q'}^*$.

of concept implementation of TWT for time aware scheduling that isolates priority traffic from best effort traffic achieving promising results on bounded latency and jitter. We leverage network calculus analysis [2] to prove that bounded latencies, required by TSN, can be achieved using this approach when both high and low priority packets are present in a STA with some violation probability that depends on channel quality. In Section 2 we model the 802.1Qbv opening gates using Network Calculus [2, 6], and in Section 3 the wireless errors using stochastic scaling [4]. We discuss results in Section 5 and conclusions in Section 6.

2 MODELLING 802.1QBV AS TDMA CURVES

The Time-Aware Shaper (TAS) in 802.1Qbv decides when to open and close each queue using a Gate Control List (GCL). The latter defines both the periodicity T_q of each queue and how long, L_q , it is open for transmission. Using Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA), a user queue q has a transmit service curve (cumulative bits processed over time), $\beta_{L, T}(t)$, given by (1)

$$\beta_{L, T}(t) = C \cdot \max \left\{ \left\lfloor \frac{t}{T} \right\rfloor L, t - \left\lceil \frac{t}{T} \right\rceil (T - L) \right\} \quad (1)$$

with C being the transmission rate and T, L the periodicity and length of the TDMA transmission opportunities. The service curve in 802.1Qbv for a queue q is given by $\beta_{L_q, T_q}^*([t - \delta_q]^+)$ where $\delta_q > 0$ is the time at which queue q gate is first opened.

Note that in 802.11Qbv, two or more queues may have their gates opened concurrently². We use an affine lower envelope of the TDMA service curve (1) to handle gate concurrency as shown in the (top) dashed line of Figure 1. The TDMA affine lower envelope for queue q in 802.1Qbv is the rate-latency function

$$\beta_q(t) = \frac{C \cdot L_q}{T_q + L_q} [t - \delta_q]^+. \quad (2)$$

3 CONCURRENT 802.1QBV OPENED GATES

When high priority queue q and low priority queue q' are opened concurrently, packets of q are transmitted ahead of those from q' .

COROLLARY 0.1 (802.1QBV HIGH PRIORITY SERVICE CURVE). *Given two queues q, q' whose gates are opened concurrently; the high priority queue q has a strict service curve*

$$\beta_q^*(t) = R_q \left[t - \left(\delta_q + \frac{l_{\max}^{q'}}{R_q} \right) \right]^+ \quad (3)$$

with $R_q = \frac{CL_q}{T_q + L_q}$ and $l_{\max}^{q'}$ the maximum packet size of the low priority queue q' .

PROOF. We mimic the proof of [2][Proposition 1.3.4]. Take the affine lower envelope of queue q defined in (1). Consider s as the start of the backlog period of queue q , hence, the arrival and departing curve at queue q is the same at that time $D_q(s) = A_q(s)$.

For 802.1Qbv is non-preemptive, if a low priority packet from q' arrives before a high priority packet from q in the interval $(s, t]$; the high priority packet will wait, i.e.

$$D_q(t) - D_q(s) \geq \beta_q(t - s) - l_{\max}^{q'} \quad (4)$$

given $D_q(s) = A_q(s)$ and $A, D \in \mathcal{F} = \{f : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \forall t \geq s : f(t) \geq f(s), f(0) = 0\}$; we know

$$D_q(t) \geq A_q(s) + \left[R_q [(t - s) - \delta_q]^+ - l_{\max}^{q'} \right]^+ \quad (5)$$

If $(t - s) > \delta_q$ (5) becomes

$$D_q(t) \geq A_q(s) + R_q \left[(t - s) - \left(\delta_q + \frac{l_{\max}^{q'}}{R_q} \right) \right]^+ \quad (6)$$

If $(t - s) \leq \delta_q$ (5) becomes $D_q(t) \geq A_q(s)$. That is, the departing flow of the high priority queue q satisfies

$$D_q(t) \geq A_q \otimes \beta_q^*(t) \quad (7)$$

with $\beta_q^*(t)$ being the rate-latency service curve with rate R_q and latency $\delta_q + \frac{l_{\max}^{q'}}{R_q}$. \square

Similarly, it is also possible to obtain the service curve for the traffic in the low priority queue q' when such queue is opened concurrently with the higher priority queue q .

COROLLARY 0.2 (802.1QBV LOW PRIORITY SERVICE CURVE). *Given two queues q, q' whose gates are opened concurrently; if the flow at q*

has a strict affine arrival curve γ_{C_q, b_q} , then the low priority queue q' has a strict service curve

$$\beta_{q'}^*(t) = (R_{q'} - C_q) \left[t - \frac{R_{q'} \delta_{q'} + b_q}{R_{q'} - C_q} \right]^+ \quad (8)$$

with $R_{q'} = \frac{CL_{q'}}{T_{q'} + L_{q'}}$.

PROOF. We again mimic the proof presented in [2] [Proposition 1.3.4]. Take the affine lower envelope of queue q' as defined in (1). Consider s' the start of the busy period, that is, $s' < s$ with s the start of the backlog period. In the interval $(s', t]$ the low priority queue departing traffic satisfies

$$D_{q'}(t) - D_{q'}(s') = \beta_{q'}(t - s') - [D_q(t) - D_q(s')] \quad (9)$$

Given that at s' there is no backlog, and the strict arrival curve for the high priority queue q , we know

$$\begin{aligned} D_q(t) - D_q(s') &= D_q(t) - A_q(s') \\ &\leq A_q(t) - A_q(s') \leq \gamma_{C_q, b_q}(t - s') \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Then, we substitute (10) in (9) to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} D_{q'}(t) - D_{q'}(s') &= D_{q'}(t) - A_{q'}(s') \\ &\geq \left[R_{q'} [(t - s) - \delta_{q'}]^+ - (C_q(t - s') + b_q) \right]^+ \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Again, depending on $(t - s)$ the above expression changes. For $(t - s) > \delta_{q'}$, (11) becomes

$$D_{q'}(t) \geq A_{q'}(s') + [(R_{q'} - C_q)(t - s') - (R_{q'} \delta_{q'} + b_q)]^+ \quad (12)$$

and with $(t - s) \leq \delta_{q'}$, inequality (11) becomes $D_{q'}(t) \geq A_{q'}(s')$. Overall, we can tell that the departing flow at the low priority queue q' satisfies

$$D_{q'}(t) \geq A_{q'} \otimes \beta_{q'}^*(t) \quad (13)$$

with $\beta_{q'}^*(t)$ being the rate-latency service curve with rate $R_{q'} - C_q$ and latency $\frac{R_{q'} \delta_{q'} + b_q}{R_{q'} - C_q}$. \square

4 RETRANSMISSIONS IN 802.11

So far, we have obtained the service curves $\beta_q^*(t), \beta_{q'}^*(t)$ of high/low priority traffic upon the opened/closed 802.1Qbv gates. By aligning gate opening with the rTWT sessions as depicted in Figure 1, channel contention is avoided since the STA has a dedicated Resource Unit (RU) in 802.11ax Multi User transmission (MU) Tx, and the rTWT session access is restricted.

However, packet errors may still occur due to channel impairments resulting in retransmissions. To deal with the latter, we use the stochastic scaling approach proposed in [4]. The idea is to send the departing traffic of 802.1Qbv $D_q(t), D_{q'}(t)$ to a wireless channel modeled with a scaling process S as shown in Figure 2. If the Tx does not succeed, the STA waits time W (as maximum) before retransmission of the i^{th} packet. This process is modelled with the scaling curve δ_W .

Following [4], we consider a binary symmetric channel modelled with stochastic scaling process $S(b) = \sum_i^b X_i, X_i \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \text{Bernoulli}(p)$,

²In this paper, we consider 2 queues for brevity. Our analysis can be easily extended to N concurrent queues.

Figure 2: When the q, q' are opened, packets $D(t)$ traverse the stochastic wireless channel S . On Tx error, δ_W represents the time it takes to realize the packet loss. Then, packets are fed-back for retransmission leading to re-entrant arrivals $\alpha^{(i)}(t)$.

with p the loss probability. We now define a stochastic scaling curve $S^\varepsilon(b) = pb + 1 - \varepsilon$ that, according to [4, Theorem 1], satisfies

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\sup_{0 \leq a \leq b} \{S(b) - S(a) - S^\varepsilon(b-a)\} \leq 0\right) \geq 1 - \varepsilon, \quad \forall b \geq 0 \quad (14)$$

that is, the queue experiencing Tx errors $S(D(t))$ is upper bounded by the outgoing traffic (which is bounded by $S^\varepsilon(D(t))$) with probability $1 - \varepsilon$.

The scaled flow $S(D(t))$ will result in retransmissions, namely, we have $\alpha^{(i)}(t)$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, N$ being the arrival curves for the i^{th} retransmissions, where $\alpha^{(0)} = A(t) = \gamma_{r,b}$ represents the original input flow. The higher the Rtx index, the higher the priority, thus each retransmission flow has arrival and service curves

$$\beta_q^{(i)} = \left[\beta - \sum_{k=i+1}^N \alpha^k\right]^+, \quad \alpha_q^{(i)} = S^\varepsilon\left(\alpha^{(i-1)} \circ \beta^{(i-1)}\right) \circ \delta_W. \quad (15)$$

Once the system is solved, we define the aggregated arrival curve for the queue q as $\alpha_q^{(Tot)} = \sum_{j=0}^N \alpha_q^{(j)}$. At this point, given the aggregated arrival curve and the service curve, Network Calculus provides bounds to obtain the maximum delay experienced by queue q using the following expression:

$$h(\alpha, \beta) := \sup_{s \geq 0} \left\{ \inf\{u \geq 0 : \alpha(s) \leq \beta(s+u)\} \right\}.$$

Note that previous curves are derived from the stochastic scaling process that model the channel, hence, they are not deterministic. In fact, as [4] highlights, the reliability of the delay bound (i.e., the probability that it holds) will be

$$\mathbb{P}\left(d(t) \leq h(\alpha^{(Tot)}, \beta)\right) \geq (1 - \varepsilon)^N \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (16)$$

with $d(t)$ representing the real delay experienced by packets at time t .

5 RESULTS

To highlight the importance of these results, we analyze two scenarios: with (i) $T = 3, L = 1$ and (ii) $T = 3, L = 2$. In both, we calculate the aggregated arrival curves for one non-overlapping queue and two overlapping queues (one with higher priority than the other). The rest of the parameters are $C = 10$, $\alpha^{(0)} = \gamma_{0.1, 0.001}$ and $N = 3$. Additionally, the violation probability of the stochastic scaling curve ε is $3.3344 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

Figure 3 shows the maximum delay experienced by the queues as a function of the loss probability p . Note that these bounds hold with a 0.999 probability. We observe that the delay is reduced with

Figure 3: Delay bound vs. wireless loss probability for different $\frac{L}{T}$ ratios. The Delay Bound holds with a 99.9% probability. We test non overlapping setups with single 802.1Qbv queues (gray), and overlapping setups with concurrent high (HP) and low priority (LP) queues (blue and red).

greater overlap. The high priority queue is less impacted compared to the low priority queue. Moreover, comparing the $L/T = 1/3$ non-overlapping case with $2/3$ overlapping case, the high priority queue in the latter case experiences less delay at the expense of the low priority queue.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We have presented stochastic bounds for TSN packets in a 802.11 deployment, with queue concurrency and retransmissions due to channel impairments. Our expressions assume the alignment of 802.1Qbv queues with 802.11 TWT sessions.

This paper provides a preliminary, simplified assessment of dense Industry 4.0 TSN wireless deployments. We intend to extend our analysis to more complex scenarios and develop a proof of concept experiments to validate our results.

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